

PARTICIPATORY MANAGEMENT IN SCHOOLS: THE SCHOOL AND THE COMMUNITY IN THE PROCESS OF INTEGRAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issue related to participatory management in schools, seeking to understand how the school and the community can act in the process of integral formation of students. It is a bibliographical research, based on the thoughts of Brazilian authors who study and analyze the subject, in the search for an organic solution about how to make such a proposal of administration prevail in teaching centers. Its social relevance lies in providing the broad public with greater conditions for discussion and understanding of the aspects of the application of power in conflict resolution and observance of the subjective public right to quality education. Its scientific relevance is focused on the fact that it brings to the academic debate a subject that, after decades of debates and proposals, was to be taken for granted in terms of its guidelines and technical applicability. What is found as a propositional evaluative merit is that this participation, when coordinated under pedagogical criteria, makes it possible to understand the problems that the school faces and to propose strategic actions that can minimize interferences and, perhaps, solve them, through partnerships and concrete actions. It is necessary for the school and its educators to rethink the daily practice, so that people have the opportunity to develop ideas and act consciously. For this, the institution needs to break paradigms that have prevailed for decades, breaking with the culture of neglect, with

automation, with individualism and starting to work proactively, synergistically and collectively with a view to improving educational quality. Only with everyone working for a single objective, community, faculty and students and administrative technicians, will an efficient and effective participatory management be achieved.

Keywords: Participatory management. School and community. Comprehensive student training.

INTRODUCTION

Participatory management appears, *a priori*, as an intense challenge for contemporary administration, especially when referring to the area of education, especially schools, because the first impact is to clarify the difference between participation and democracy. The former will only exist within a democratic regime of law, in which citizens have the right to participate in the political arena, where the elements that will compose and guide administrative decisions are determined in advance.

In Brazil, since the enactment of the Federal Constitution of 1988 and the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (Law 9394; BRAZIL, 1988; 1996) which in their respective texts express the decentralization of the administration of public education establishments and the school being one of these privileged fields could not be left out of the discussion.

In this same sense, the constituents propose that the principle of school management be based on a communion of ideas shared by all those involved in the educational process. Hence, the undertaking of participatory management was born, along the lines of the Democracy that has governed the Republic since then.

According to Lustosa (2020), participatory management is characterized by technical and pedagogical articulations, all of which are aimed at discussing collective educational goals that can be guided by reflective planning of pedagogical actions to be developed throughout the school year and even for a longer period, enabling the elaboration of a strategic action plan. Therefore, “participatory management is solidified through collective and reflective planning of teaching and learning situations that aim at a common educational interest, which share information, problematizing situations” (Lustosa, 2020, p. 34)

Such a proposal requires the active participation of the school's stakeholders, in which each one understands their role and the responsibility that falls to them in pedagogical practice and in the elaboration of their praxis, in which the objective of the entire systematization is the promotion of teaching and learning.

Participatory management presents proposals for a new type of administration that involves many people, many opinions and diversity of knowledge. In this context, this management model does not exclude the traditional one, but adds to this new information, more effective practices, improving it for a new time, new demands and new needs. It is the updating of management to deal with the changes that occur in all sectors of human life, be it political, social or educational (CEZÁRIO et al, 2020).

Lima et al (2014) argue that the field of school administration has undergone several transformations in recent times, seeking an ideal way to establish its goals. Knowing that the pedagogical proposal is the school's compass, so that it can find biases that transform plans into practice, the concept of administrator has been replaced by that of manager today. The evolution of the management concept has attributed new perspectives to the importance of the action carried out, leading the school community to think from the perspective of developing strategies in daily educational life (CEZÁRIO et al, 2020).

Sobrinho (2020, p. 8) highlights that “the main characteristic of participatory management is the use of collective decision-making, where employees share a significant degree of decisions with their superiors.”

Here we find a major misunderstanding regarding the practical meaning of participatory management, because it does not directly involve decision-making by managers. What happens is that the collective acts directly on the proposals that will be analyzed by managers and considered in a way that represents the broadest desire expressed, sometimes representing the will of the majority; but without the obligation for this to stand out from the strategic administrative process of the school.

The principle of participatory management in schools seeks to integrate members representing direct management, teaching staff, students and management team, parents and employees in general, based on the pedagogical principle that the school is a place of education and human development, par excellence, therefore, the participation of all those who make it up, as an educational body, is essential.

All the interest in this change in the school's thinking and actions, in relation to its pedagogical and administrative processes, aims at better integration of the student with teaching, providing better results in their learning and the expectation of a more promising integration with the world that awaits them. Thus, for this work, the following guiding question is assumed as a problem situation: In what way does the participation of the pedagogical team, teachers and the community surrounding the school in the school's educational management processes make the didactic-pedagogical situations more efficient, with better learning rates?

PARTICIPATORY MANAGEMENT

It is very common to infer the error of confusing participation with democracy. The latter allows for broad participation in processes; but, even in this sense, there are very clear limitations regarding the role of each person involved in the stages and the decision is not one of them. Thus, it is worth clarifying that, in the conception of Rodrigues et al (2020, p. 113),

Participatory management is something that comes from a democratic, collective decision-making power that is chosen comprehensively with the common good in mind. Therefore, this management process requires leadership power, since a manager must participate actively and cohesively in all moments of choice for the institution. This participation must be understood as a democratic management model that takes into account all opinions about the future and the projects proposed to improve the institution.

This action of thinking about the problems of the school and the education it develops, aiming to meet the desires of the population that benefits from its pedagogical processes, represents an advance and a guarantee that the decisions taken by the Administration are aimed at the interest of the collective and that the objectives become an integral part of everyone's responsibility.

This is a vision that, even though it has been advocated for many millennia, since Athens, Greece, with the institute of participatory democracy (SOBRINHO, 2020), in educational institutions, its insertion has taken place since 1996, with the promulgation of the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (Law 9394/96), on December 20 of that year, which states that one of the principles of education will be based on the democratic management of education (Brazil, LDB 9394 - Art 3, Inc. VIII, 1996).

Participatory management assumes the development of a long-term strategy for the school, where the interest is the results arising from the pedagogical work that it carries out. In this sense, Lück (2010) will state that,

Effective participation in school presupposes that teachers, collectively organized, discuss and analyze the pedagogical problems they experience in interaction with the school organization and that, based on this analysis, they determine ways to overcome the difficulties they consider most in need of attention and assume a commitment to promoting transformation in school practices [...] (LÜCK, 2010, p. 33).

What can be inferred from this thought is that participation should have as its main objective the performance of students in relation to their learning gains, which already makes it clear that teaching activities are the target object of analyses, interpretations and interventions,

in which everyone seeks a viable and plausible solution to a problem that current education faces, without many prospects of a solution, namely the low results rates in external assessments, applied by the State and by international organizations.

Here, a challenging question arises: what can be done so that students can overcome the challenges of learning the program content? And, once this has been discovered, a new challenge arises: how can we do it? Even if a solution is found to this overwhelming problem, what is advocated is that it is not up to the school, on its own, to solve it, based on the concept that those who teach and produce the lessons are the teachers and, when it comes to explaining the academic-school performance of students to their parents and guardians, this task falls to them, who in turn transfer the responsibility for the failure of some [*or of entire classes*] to their respective families.

Strictly speaking,

Participatory management is a unity of principles and actions that enables and mediates people's involvement in decision-making necessary to promote goals for the good of all. In addition, it aims to improve relationships in the school environment, as it allows everyone to participate in giving opinions, deciding on actions, planning goals, that is, valuing the ideas given by everyone regardless of their position or function within the school. All those involved – parents, students, staff and teachers – in participatory management feel motivated, enjoy being part of it and feel recognized. With this, they open the way for innovation, as they feel and think like managers of the school organization (ARAÚJO, 2010, pp. 14-15).

By bringing families and the community closer to the school and its pedagogical project, it is possible to understand the difficulties and limitations that each of them presents and to develop ways of helping them so that they do not feel helpless in the face of the reality that surrounds them or guilty for not being able to offer better conditions to their children, which ends with the school being blamed, a kind of transfer of responsibility and guilt.

When the family and the entire pedagogical-school team come together for a common goal, the result is that the potential strengths of each group, in particular, gain power, highlighting what they have best to offer to the other in the form of mutual help, because the goal is only one, the achievement of value by the students and the more they reveal themselves to be superior, the more the school and its team gain in authority and social recognition.

Based on this thought, in Lück's (2017a) conception, management needs to mobilize the school community in order to ensure that everyone develops the skills and autonomy of the subjects to decide, project goals and coordinate people with the objective of solving problems

and guaranteeing learning. Participation allows educational actors to become protagonists in the planning of pedagogical actions that project quality education.

With this pragmatic vision of participatory management, teachers can develop their teaching programs in an inter and transdisciplinary way, because once they dialogue, not only as people, but as scientists who work in apparently distinct areas, they discover, through these interactions, that in many points their epistemological fields overlap, which allows for new forms of dialectics and conflict resolution.

Once again, Heloisa Lück's thinking shines through, arguing that participation is a didactic-pedagogical way of sharing and observing points of view that make activities effective, resulting in pragmatic, real feedback in learning, as well as in internal and external evaluations (LÜCK, 2017b).

PARTICIPATORY MANAGEMENT AND ITS IMPACTS ON TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESSES

The history of participatory management dates back to the 1960s, when it was recognized that contemporary organizational life is highly complex. In the late 1970s, educators and researchers around the world began to pay greater attention to participatory management, seeking to enhance the effectiveness of schools as organizations. Realizing that it is not possible for a principal to personally solve all the problems and issues related to his or her school, the participatory approach emphasizes that, for the organization to be successful, principals must seek out the specific knowledge and experience of their subordinates. Principals base themselves on the concept of shared authority, through which power and responsibility are delegated to representatives of the school community.

Many studies on good school results in developed countries, particularly in the United States, have identified some characteristics positively associated with effective schools, including the importance of leadership, culture and organizational structures.

Democratic management is a way of managing an institution in a way that enables participation, transparency and democracy, where the participation of each subject is fundamental and the recognition of their ideas and contribution must be independent of the hierarchical level.

For Delors (2001), education has a special responsibility in building a more caring, humane and ethical world, and it is up to school management to think about how to incorporate this concept that is becoming increasingly essential for a fair and egalitarian society. However,

this awareness of participatory management does not occur naturally among all groups in the school community; on the contrary, it needs to be instigated, stimulated, experienced and learned by everyone.

The idea that is defended is that of shared responsibility, that is, school education is a social task that must be developed by society. The effective and active participation of different social segments in decision-making makes everyone aware that they are actors in the history that is made in the day-to-day life of the school.

Participation presupposes joint action by a collective in favor of a common good, already defined as being of social interest. LS Vygotsky (1896-1934), in his investigations, together with collaborators, found a very interesting social phenomenon of learning, which he classified as *the Zone of Proximal Development*, a space for symbolic exchanges of knowledge in which those with more experience teach those with less experience and thus, new fields of knowledge are formed that are validated through well-designed and defined assessments regarding the object of learning. "In this paradigm, the origin of the psyche is social and is guaranteed by the subject's participation in activities shared with other social individuals, within the framework of cultural processes organized in an active context" (Alessandroni, 2017, p. 47).

School autonomy refers to the construction of the identity of the educational institution based on the recognition of its capacity to develop its own educational project through the adoption of shared management, thus making the school capable of directly managing the resources allocated to the development and maintenance of education.

Although there is no single way to implement a participatory management system, it is possible to identify some principles, values and priorities in the effective construction of this management. Libâneo states that:

Participation is the main means of ensuring democratic management of the school, enabling the involvement of professionals and users in the decision-making process and in the functioning of the school organization. In addition, it provides a better understanding of the objectives and goals, the organizational structure and its dynamics, the school's relations with the community, and favors a closer relationship between teachers, students, and parents. (LIBÂNEO, 2004, p.79)

For the author, the concept of participation is based on that of autonomy, which means the ability of people and groups to lead their own lives. Autonomy is opposed to authoritarian forms of decision-making and, therefore, a participatory democratic management model has

autonomy as one of its most important principles, implying the free choice of objectives and work processes and the joint construction of the work environment.

In the philosophical precept, autonomy is conceived as the ability that a person or an organization has to self-govern, that is, to function governed by its own rules. Gadotti (2001, p. 47) states that autonomy refers to the “creation of new social relations, which oppose existing authoritarian relations. Being the opposite of standardization, it admits difference and presupposes partnership.”

For this reason, an autonomous school does not act in isolation, but in constant exchange with society. The autonomy and democratic management of the school are part of the very nature of the pedagogical act and represent decision-making about its objectives and its form of organization, enabling relative independence from the central power to chart its own path, with the participation of teachers, students, staff, parents and the nearby community, who become co-responsible for the school's success.

Day-to-day relationships in the educational field demonstrate the social and political model of the environment in which it is inserted. Therefore, in theory, it should make its line of action clear. Gadotti emphasizes that,

The principle of democratic management and school autonomy implies a complete change in the education system. Our current education system still follows the principle of centralization, in contrast to the constitutional principle of democratization of management (GADOTTI 2004, p. 49).

It is understood that democratic management should be understood as a way of managing an institution based on principles such as: decentralization, participation, transparency and democracy. In *Participatory Management*, some basic characteristics of fundamental importance in the process can be highlighted: Elaboration of the Political Pedagogical Project in a collective and participatory manner; Constitution of a School Council; Direct election of the director.

For Gadotti (2004, p. 49), “participation and democratization in a public education system is the most practical form of citizenship training”. In other words, it means that the participation of all those involved in the day-to-day running of the school are fundamental and essential pieces for the formation of a new society.

Schools are among the main institutions responsible for social development, as they are institutions to which society attributes the responsibility of providing formal education, creating opportunities for individuals to develop, decide and think. Schools are intended to be democratic in management, and therefore must work on civic awareness, that is, prioritizing

the collective, with a view to providing quality education.

School management based on principles of autonomy, participation and democracy is present in the Federal Constitution of Brazil, which 1988, appoints to the need for management with the participation of the school community: Art. 206; IV guarantees participatory management in public education, ensuring the democratic nature of education so that “public institutions can create a political-educational culture of exercising the principle and practice of democracy in their daily lives” (Brazil, 1988, sp).

Autonomy is a process of conquest and not of delegation. Autonomy is achieved with competence, through the interaction of the school community – managers, students, staff, parents, and those around the school – in a participatory management.

In order to establish democratic and participatory relations between schools and the community/society, it is necessary to effectively promote democratization in management. The theory and practice of educational management must be rethought in order to eliminate formal controls and strengthen controls based on results assessment, encouraging the autonomy of schools and school units, with the participation of the school community (family, staff, faculty and students) in the social control of the school. Such understandings and practices are linked to the new role of the State and its agencies and to a reformulation of professional training courses in education.

Management based on democratic principles and determinations is essential to establish a culture of participation without which clientelism, welfare and corruption, which perpetuate the system of domination and underdevelopment, will not be eradicated. Management based on the democratic order and participatory perspectives is considered to have a pedagogical character, as it transforms the school into a laboratory of autonomous citizenship.

School management promotes, within the school community, the reallocation and sharing of responsibilities that aim to energize the legitimacy of the school system, simply by fulfilling educational objectives more effectively. However, all those involved must contribute effectively, taking responsibility for implementing the decisions made together, in order to obtain the best results in the search for quality education.

In order for schools to become more powerful and achieve their political and pedagogical autonomy, they urgently need to achieve participatory democratic management, as these are essential conditions for promoting quality education and, fundamentally, they constitute an instrument for building a new citizenship. Thus, institutional democratization becomes a gateway, a path, so that pedagogical practice can effectively become a social practice and can contribute to strengthening the broader democratic process.

A principal capable of exercising participatory leadership can determine the difference between a stagnant school and a school on the move. In order for quality teaching to occur effectively, the educational manager needs to remain in constant contact with teachers so that each professional, student and parent feels that the school is part of their lives. It is also necessary to go beyond indirect intervention in the work of teachers. The principal must act as an educational leader and directly influence the professional behavior of educators, stimulating creativity and not leaving the establishment of standards in the background, confronting, correcting and training. Valuing the performance of teachers, knowing that receiving recognition motivates them to do their job better and better, is essential.

It is clear from the different moments of reflection that the social function of the school is something that is intertwined with the unfolding of history itself, in its different manifestations. In a world undergoing a globalization process, new demands are placed on schools and on those who participate in their management. New pillars for education in the 21st century are being established: learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together and learning to be, to name just a few of the multiple learning processes necessary for a world undergoing change.

It is important to remember that for this to happen, it is necessary to train the professionals who work there, as well as the school community itself, so that participatory management can take place. It is also necessary to free the school from the marks of authoritarianism, which requires redefining its profile and role, with a view to implementing participatory planning, which must also include representatives from the internal community (principal, vice-principal, teachers, students and staff) and external community (parents, agencies/institutions, organized civil society, etc.).

It is worth noting that the democratization of education involves the democratization of the knowledge produced, and this will only be possible through the construction of a new type of management that seeks to transform society and schools through the participation of all. The talk about democratic management is present in almost all discourses on education. In practice, it is known that it is not easy to break paradigms and transform overnight the type of traditional management that has survived for centuries.

It is necessary for the manager to know how to balance the lack of some administrative skills with the help of some collaborators who have other skills that will complete the collective work. Delegating powers is a key point in all collective work, since training, mediating and guiding are the essence of the management role. The manager must dedicate a large part of his

time to integrating with his team. Preparing the school community for democratic management is the essence of the transformation of the education system.

Schools and their educators need to rethink their daily practices so that people have the opportunity to develop ideas and act consciously. To do this, the institution needs to break paradigms that have prevailed for decades, breaking with the culture of neglect, automation, and individualism, and starting to work proactively, synergistically, and collectively to improve educational quality. Only with everyone working towards a single goal—the community, faculty, students, and administrative staff—will efficient and effective participatory management be achieved.

CONCLUSION

With the advent of democratization in Brazil in 1985, many changes in the management systems of institutions were advocated and, after the promulgation of the Federal Constitution of 1988, such ideals were highlighted and, as is customary, education and the entire process it encompasses was included in such discussion until it gained the status of law, in the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (LAW 9394/96), which determines the management of school units based on principles of social participation.

This is characterized as a watershed in the history of Brazilian education, because despite there already being a very strong link between civil society and schools, this did not appear as a power that had been duly legislated by the competent authorities.

Even so, this issue remains an amalgam to be interpreted and resolved, given that only in Brazil is such an administrative conduct adopted, in which all members of the community have the power to broadly discuss the problems that the school faces, interfering in the management of the system. As clarified in the text, participatory management is not synonymous with democratic management, in which the former assumes participation in discussions and projects related to the development and application of administrative methods, ending its power there, while the latter gains decision-making power at the same level as the management team, by all members and employees of the unit.

The participatory management process can be seen as a social achievement; however, it is necessary to clarify the limits of power granted by current legislation to each party involved, otherwise a state of conflict [*almost*] impossible to be resolved by the administration will be created. It is never less important to clarify that administrative decisions are the prerogative of

the manager and function as action strategies, determinants that guide the organization of the business.

Furthermore, this social participation must prioritize the quality of the ideas presented and how it will influence the final decision-making, understanding that education is a long-term process, and that each year its cycle restarts with new students entering the system, in order to complete a cycle of almost two decades, only in regular basic education.

REFERENCES

ALESSANDRONI, Nicolás. **Imagination, creativity and fantasy in Lev S. Vygotski: an approach to his sociocultural approach.** (2017). In: *Actualidades en Psicología* , 31(122), p. 45-60. La Plata. Available at: <http://revistas.ucr.ac.cr/index.php/actualidades> . Accessed on 01/17/2022.

ARAÚJO, Rosângela Maria Garcia de. **Participatory management and the role of the principal in the search for transformation: theoretical and practical reflections.** Specialization (latu sensu in Educational Management). Ceará: Federal University of Santa Maria – Education Center, 2010.

BRAZIL. **Law No. 9394**, of December 20, 1996. Official Gazette of the Union, No. 248, 1996.

BRAZIL. **Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil of 1988** . 71st Ed. Brasília: Senate Printing Office, 2017.

CEZÁRIO, Danilo de Sousa; GOMES, Michele da Silva; ALBUQUERQUE, Maria Elisiéth Anacleto de; SOUZA, Rosângela Tavares Dantas de. **Reflections on participatory management** : contributions from the democratic educational model. In: 6th National Education Congress - CONEDU. Fortaleza, 2020.

DELLORS, Jacques. **Education: a treasure to be discovered** - report to UNESCO of the International Commission on Education for the 21st Century. São Paulo: Cortez, 2001.

GADOTTI, Moacir. **Citizen School.** 10th Ed.

LIBÂNEO, José Carlos. **School Organization and Management: Theory and Practice.** 5th Ed. Goiânia: Alternativa, 2004.

Functions of educational management: Planning, organization, direction and control in municipal schools of Aquiraz-CE, Brazil. **Electronic Journal of Education** , v. 8, n. 3, 2014, p. 127-146.

LUCK, Heloísa. **Leadership in school management.** 6th Ed. Petropolis: Vozes, 2010.

LUCK, Heloísa. **Participatory management in schools**. Petropolis: Vozes. Management Notebooks Series, 2017a.

LUCK, Heloísa. **Educational management: a paradigmatic issue**. Petrópolis: Vozes, 2017b. Series: Management Notebooks.

LUSTOSA, Fabiane Fernandes Torres. **Participatory management** : knowledge and practices in a public educational institution in Marabá. Course completion work (Undergraduate degree in Pedagogy). Pará: Federal University of Southern and Southeastern Pará – Marabá Campus, 2020.

RODRIGUES, Emanuel Márcio da Silva et al. Participatory management: The stance of the school manager as a mediator in the decision-making process. **Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal Knowledge Center**. Year 05, Ed. 01, Vol. 07, 2020, pp. 107-133.

SOBRINHO, Poliana da Silva. **Participatory Management and its Influence on Organizational Climate**: a bibliographic research. Course Conclusion Work (Undergraduate Degree in Administration). Brasília: Aparecido dos Santos University Center of the Central Plateau – UNICEPLAC, 2020.